

TEACHING VOCABULARY THROUGH READING IN TEACHING ENGLISH AT B1 LEVEL

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Abstract: Teaching vocabulary at the intermediate (B1) level is a difficult task because students require more attention than their enthusiasm for learning. According to the CEFR, B1 level candidates in ESL learning (i.e., intermediate independent users of the target language) are required to understand the key point of straightforward, normal feedback on familiar matters experienced on a daily basis at work, education, etc. Additionally, they are required to be in a situation to manage most circumstances prone to emerge when they are utilizing the objective language at home or abroad, in different social settings. They can create a straightforward intelligible book on subjects of individual or social interest and they can depict encounters and occasions, dreams, expectations, and aspirations and momentarily offer reasons and clarifications for thoughts and plans.

Keywords: vocabulary, learners, knowledge, scheme, five-step procedure, technique, etymology, acquainting, prefixes, suffixes.

INTRODUCTION. In this day and age, the interest to the experts who is ace in unknown dialects is creating step by step in our free republic now. Specifically, English is additionally viewed as one of the requesting dialects of our life. Obviously, it's anything but a mystery, that there is being focused on the showing English language. To make an agreeably grew, profoundly taught, present day thinking youthful age the main the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov marked a Decree "On measures to additionally improve the learning arrangement of unknown dialects." Currently, the field of English Language Teaching started to address phonetic and social variety; as opposed to zeroing in on training perspectives identified with the English language. Presumably, English is the most famous unknown dialect. Numerous Uzbek individuals wish to learn for instructive, monetary and social reasons, a reality that applies to numerous other non-English talking nations also. Generally, vocabulary used to be offered to students as records and jargon guidance has zeroed in on having understudies look into word implications and retain them. This instructing approach gives just the surface and transient learning of words. The Texas Reading Initiate found that students who simply memorize word meanings frequently have troubles applying the information in definitions and often make mistakes about the meaning. A word utilized in various settings may have various implications: hence basically learning meanings of a word without instances of where and when the word happens won't assist students with completely understanding its significance. Learning an isolated list of words without reference to the context is a memorization exercise that makes it difficult for learners to use the words in spoken and written language. Looking at the context in which the word appears seems to be the best way of learning vocabulary and learn how its meaning relates to the words around it. In addition, a methodology that incorporates definitions, just as its utilization in the content, can create full and adaptable information on word implications. When students are given several sentences that use a word in different ways they begin to see

how a meaning of words can change and shift depending on its context. Learners need to see words in different contexts in order to learn them thoroughly. Honey field stresses the importance of context by arguing that even with a functional vocabulary of 3000 most frequently occurring items in English learners will not still know approximately 20 percent of items, they will come across in an unsimplified text. Too much dictionary work can kill all interests in reading and even interfere with comprehension” because learners become more concerned with individual items and less aware of the context, which gives them meaning. It is also results in every slow and inefficient reading “ Therefore, good learners often acquire much of their vocabulary through independent reading are learned through context. In any case, Watanable cases that "Albeit coincidental learning of jargon through setting is conceivable, it isn't generally productive" Indeed, learning vocabulary must be meaningful to students. This occurs when a learner is able to relate new words to his/her prior knowledge or scheme. Schema is defined by Pearson and Spiro as little pictures or associations you conjure up in your head when you read a word or sentence. The rich literary context for each word not only provides a literary context, but also exposes students to fiction and non-fiction by various authors. These four stages of word knowledge were summarized by Dale and O'Rourke as follows: I have never seen it before I have never heard of it, but I do not know what it means. I recognized it in the context- it has something to do with... I know it. Seeing vocabulary in rich context provided by the authentic texts, rather than isolated vocabulary drills produced strong vocabulary learning. Rich and strong vocabulary instruction goes beyond definitional knowledge; it gets students actively engaged in using and thinking about word meaning, associates with other words, guessing from the context. If the students decide that a term is worth guessing, they will use Nation and Coady's five-step procedure: 1. Determine the parts of the speech of unknown words 2. Look at immediate context and simplify it if necessary. 3. Look at the wider context. This involves inspecting the proviso with the obscure word and its relationship to the encompassing conditions and sentences.. 4. Guess the meaning of the unknown word 5. Check that the guess is correct. The couple of investigations of speculating words from setting demonstrate that an enormous extent of the obscure words can be effectively managed thusly. As it was mentioned before, Linda Diamond and Linda Galton pointed out that one of the words of learning strategies is contextual, involves inferring the meaning of unfamiliar word by examining the text surrounding it. Instruction in contextual analysis generally involves teaching students to use both general and specific types of context clues.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Several writes describe various types of clues that can provide information to help in guessing. Brown lists definitions, learner's experience of the world contrast, interference and analysis. Steinberg lists grammar, punctuation, definition, contrast, connectives, reference words, word analysis and the learner's experience and common sense. But all these approaches lack in semantic procedure to follow. Only Chanrasegaran uses a questioning procedure to guide learners in guessing, but this is dependent on the teacher's choice of questions.

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